

Viscosity of multicomponent gas mixtures

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Viscosity of ternary, quaternary and quinary mixtures have been determined by the Pandey-Prajapati method. These values have been compared with those obtained by Mason-Saxena and Lindsay-Bromley methods.

In design calculations and control of chemical process equipment, the transport and thermodynamic properties of mixtures of many components are required. The design calculations and control of fluid flow equipment, in particular, requires the viscosity of the fluids. As the number of components of the fluid mixtures increases, the possible number of mixtures of different composition and hence the necessary number of viscosity measurements become very large. It thus becomes necessary to predict or estimate the viscosities of multicomponent fluid mixtures by some method, which should, ideally, give reasonably good results and yet be simple enough.

Theoretical :

The phenomenon of viscosity and diffusion are not appreciably affected by presence of internal degrees of freedom. The theory of monoatomic gases holds good for polyatomic molecules also, provided the molecules are not too non-spherical. The coefficient of thermal conductivity is significantly affected by the contributions due to internal and translational energy. Eucken modified the Chapman-Enskog relation as

$$\lambda = \eta (R/M) \left[\frac{C_v}{R} + \frac{9}{4} \right] \quad (1)$$

where λ is coefficient of thermal conductivity, η the coefficient of viscosity, M the molecular weight, R the gas constant and C_v the molal specific heat at constant volume.

The expression for viscosity and thermal conductivity presented by Hirschfelder, Curtiss and Bird¹ describes transport properties of mixtures well but expressions are cumbersome and the calculations become tedious as the number of components increases. The simple Wassiljewa equation has been most extensively used to estimate the transport properties of gaseous mixtures. Recently, a slightly modified Wassiljewa equation has been applied for the evaluation of thermal conductivity of binary liquid mixtures.

The Wassiljewa equation can be written as

$$P_m = \frac{P_i}{[1 + A_{ij}(x_j/x_i)]} \quad (2)$$

where P_m is either viscosity or thermal conductivity of mixture, P_i and P_j are viscosities or thermal conductivities of pure components i and j , x_i and x_j are mole fractions, A_{ij} and A_{ji} are parameters called Wassiljewa coefficients.

Various semi-empirical relations have been proposed for estimating parameter A_{ij} . Lindsay and Bromley² proposed,

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + \left\{ (\eta_i / \eta_j) \cdot (M_j / M_i)^{3/4} \frac{T + S_i}{T + S_j} \right\}^{1/2} \right]^2 \frac{T + S_{ij}}{T + S_i} \quad (3)$$

where η_i , M_i and S_i are the viscosity, molecular weight and Sutherland's constant respectively of component i at absolute temperature, T . $S_{ij} = (S_i \cdot S_j)^{1/2}$ when both gases are non-polar.

Mason and Saxena³ suggested another equation for calculation of parameter A_{ij} .

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}} \left(1 + \frac{M_i}{M_j} \right)^{-1/2} \left[1 + (\eta_i + \eta_j)^{1/2} \frac{(M_j)^{1/4}}{M_i} \right]^2 \quad (4)$$

Pandey and Prajapati⁴ have utilised Hirschfelder-Eucken approximation and derived the following modified Lindsay-Bromley and Mason-Saxena equation for thermal conductivity of binary gas mixtures as

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + \left\{ (\lambda_i / \lambda_j) \cdot (M_i / M_j)^{1/4} \frac{T + S_i}{T + S_j} \right\}^{1/2} \right]^2$$

$$\frac{T + S_{ij}}{T + S_i} \quad (5)$$

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{8}} \left(1 + \frac{M_i}{M_j} \right)^{-1/2} \left[1 + (\lambda_i / \lambda_j)^{1/2} \left(\frac{M_j}{M_i} \right)^{1/4} \right]^2 \quad (6)$$

and for polyatomic gases,

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + \left\{ (\lambda_i / \lambda_j) \cdot (M_i / M_j)^{1/4} \cdot \frac{(4/15)C_{v,i} + (3/5)R_i}{(4/15)C_{v,j} + (3/5)R_j} \right\} \left(\frac{T + S_i}{T + S_j} \right)^{-1/2} \right]^2 \frac{T + S_{ij}}{T + S_i} \quad (7)$$

or

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + \left\{ (\lambda_i / \lambda_j) \cdot (M_i / M_j)^{1/4} \cdot \frac{Cp_j + 1.25R_j}{Cp_i + 1.25R_i} \left(\frac{T + S_i}{T + S_j} \right)^{-1/2} \right\} \right]^2 \frac{T + S_{ij}}{T + S_i} \quad (8)$$

Eqs. (5) and (8) in conjunction with Wassiljewa eq. (2) have been employed to estimate the viscosity of noble gaseous mixtures with the only difference that values of pure component viscosity has been substituted in these equations in place of pure component thermal conductivity. The eqs. (5) and (8) thus become

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + \left\{ (\eta_i / \eta_j) \cdot (M_i / M_j)^{1/4} \cdot \frac{T + S_i}{T + S_j} \right\} \right]^2 \frac{T + S_{ij}}{T + S_i} \quad (9)$$

$$A_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \left[1 + \left\{ (\eta_i / \eta_j) \cdot (M_i / M_j)^{1/4} \cdot \frac{Cp_j + 1.25R_j}{Cp_i + 1.25R_i} \left(\frac{T + S_i}{T + S_j} \right)^{-1/2} \right\} \right]^2 \frac{T + S_{ij}}{T + S_i} \quad (10)$$

Results and discussion

Values of viscosity of ternary system, viz. helium + neon + argon at 373 and 473 K, two quaternary systems, viz. helium + nitrogen + oxygen + carbondioxide at 273 and 313 K, neon + argon + krypton + xenon at 373 K and 473 K and one quinary system helium + neon + argon + krypton + xenon at 373 K have been calculated according to Pandey-Prajapati⁴ method and presented in Tables 1–4. The calcu-

Table 1. Viscosity of ternary mixture of He-Ne-Ar at 373 K and 1 atm.

Mole fractions : He – 0.1754; Ne – 0.5575; Ar – 0.2670.

$\eta_{m(\text{expt})} = 32.27 \mu\text{Pas}$

	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
η_m	32.74	31.21	31.20
% Deviation	1.16	-3.58	-3.61

Viscosity of the ternary mixture of He-Ne-Ar at 473 K

(A) Mole fractions : He – 0.1754; Ne – 0.2018; Ar – 0.6228.

$\eta_{m(\text{Expt})} = 37.52 \mu\text{Pas}$

(B) Mole fractions : He – 0.1984; Ne – 0.2166; Ar – 0.5850.

$\eta_{m(\text{Expt})} = 34.25 \mu\text{Pas}$

(A)	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
η_m	38.27	36.41	36.31
% Deviation	-2.02	-2.96	-3.22
(B)	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
η_m	29.43	27.81	27.81
% Deviation	1.99	-3.60	-3.60

Table 2. Viscosity of quaternary gas mixture of He-N₂-O₂-CO₂ at 273 and 313 K

Set I : Mole fractions : He – 0.1; N₂ – 0.5; O₂ – 0.25; CO₂ – 0.15.

$\eta_{m(\text{expt})}$ at 273 K = 178.5 μPas ; $\eta_{m(\text{expt})}$ at 313 K = 197.2 μPas

	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
T = 273 K			
η_m	168.8	168.7	170.9
% Deviation	-5.4	-5.4	-4.2
T = 313 K			
η_m	188.0	185.6	184.2
% Deviation	-4.6	-5.8	-6.5

Set II : Mole fractions : He – 0.25; N₂ – 0.25; O₂ – 0.25; CO₂ – 0.25.

$\eta_{m(\text{expt})}$ at 273 K = 182.6 μPas ; $\eta_{m(\text{expt})}$ at 313 K = 208.6 μPas

	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
T = 273 K			
η_m	168.8	163.0	166.0
% Deviation	-7.3	-10.7	-8.4
T = 313 K			
η_m	188.3	178.7	175.4
% Deviation	-9.5	-14.3	-15.9

Table 3. Viscosity of equimolar quaternary mixture of Ne-Ar-Kr-Xe at 373 and 473 K

$\eta_{m(\text{expt})}$ at 373 K = 31.50 μPas ; $\eta_{m(\text{expt})}$ at 473 K = 38.09 μPas			
	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
T = 373 K			
η_m	31.16	29.80	29.80
% Deviation	-1.06	-5.37	-5.39
T = 473 K			
η_m	36.59	34.77	34.88
% Deviation	-3.48	-8.71	-8.42

Table 4. Viscosity of equimolar quinary mixture of He-Ne-Ar-Kr-Xe at 373 K

$\eta_{m(\text{expt})} = 31.8 \mu\text{Pas}$			
	Mason-Saxena	Lindsay-Bromley	Pandey-Prajapati
η_m	32.19	28.46	28.7
% Deviation	1.23	-10.50	-9.74

lated values are compared with those obtained by Mason-Saxena³ and Lindsay-Bromley methods. Employing these three methods, the deviations are found to range from 3 to 10% in case of noble gases.

The results yielded by the approximate expression for interaction parameters, A_{ij} and A_{ji} by Pandey-Prajapati and Lindsay-Bromley methods are almost of same order. Although Lindsay-Bromley is oldest and most extensively tested for thermal conductivity of low pressures binary gas mixtures with average error of just 1.9% but it is evident

from the tables that the results are not so promising in case of viscosity of gas mixtures. On the contrary, Mason-Saxena method, which has been, till now, tested for good agreement with experimental values of monoatomic noble gas mixtures with standard deviations of 2% only. Occurrence of large error may be attributed to the fact that one of the components in the mixture is either helium or hydrogen.

Experimental values of η_m and pure component viscosities are obtained from the literature¹ for ternary mixtures of helium, neon and argon. For the quaternary system of helium, nitrogen, oxygen and carbondioxide, the values of pure component viscosities and those of η_m have been obtained from ref. (6) and for the quinary mixture from ref. (6).

References

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